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Research Article

PREVALENCE OF DEPRESSION AMONG CHRONIC HCV PATIENT A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY IN MIRPURKHAS

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Abstract:

Aim: Aim of Study is to find out the prevalence of depression among HCV patients and to find out correlation between depression, risk factors, associated diseases and complications develop among chronic HCV patients.

Methodology: it is a Cross-sectional Study conducted in July to August 2019 in Liver Opd and ward Muhammad medical college Mirpurkhas. 53 Patients having hepatitis for more than 6 months were included in the study while newly diagnosed cases were excluded. Data Collected through Face to face interview was conducted by using closed ended questionnaire (PH-8). Data entered and analysis done by SPSS version 24.

Results: 11.3% were Mildly Positive for Depression, 43.3% were moderately positive, 37.7% were moderately severe positive while only 7.5% were severely positive. Overall depression was found in age group of 41-50 & 51-60. While out of total depressed patient 69.9% patients were associated with other diseases. From Patients who develop the complications 7 presents was with mild depression, 11 presents was with moderate depression & 54% was with severe depression. From patients who were taking ribavirin out of which 19.4% develop mild depression, 48.4% develop moderate depression and 32.2% develop moderately severe depression. Out of patients with mild depression no one was taking antidepressants while with moderate depression 8% were getting antidepressants, with moderately severe depression 12% were taking antidepressants, 50% patients with severe depression were getting antidepressant treatment.

Conclusion: We concluded that all the patients with HCV were having some degree of depression. The prevalence of depression was found to be Mild depression 11.3%, Moderate depression 43.3%, moderately severe depression 37.5%, and severe depression 7. While 37.3% patient develop further complications like hepatic encephalopathy etc.

Keywords: Prevalence, Depression, Chronic Hcv, Patient, Cross Sectional Study, Mirpurkhas.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection is one of the main causes of chronic liver disease worldwide affecting an estimated 170 million people. There is an increase prevalence of psychiatric comorbidity in chronic hepatitis C patients compare to general population that may lead to contraindication of antiviral therapy (INF alpha). Mental health issues may also reduce the quality of life and interferes with treatment compliance. Rates of depression have been reported in the range of 22% to 59% of patients with HCV according to a research. A study also showed a rate of Major depression 36% moderate to severe suicide risk 18%. The incidence of depression is increased in patients with major chronic medical disorders, such as conditions involving immune and inflammatory mechanisms. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection are the major causes of chronic hepatitis. Depression is a very common complaint among chronic hepatitis patients who do not receive any antiviral be beneficial in disease management. Since depression worsens the

outcomes of comorbid physical conditions, an accurate estimation of depression prevalence in chronic hepatitis B and C (CHB, CHC) patients was reported to be needed, in order to decide on the need for depression screening in patients with hepatitis. Previous studies showed higher rates of depression in CH patients and CHC patients who did not receive prior anti-viral therapy. This study was performed to further compare the prevalence and severity of depression in CHC patients, and healthy participants.

METHODOLOGY:

It is a Cross-sectional Study conducted in July to August 2019 in Liver Opd and ward Muhammad medical college Mirpurkhas. 53 Patients having hepatitis for more than 6 months were included in the study while newly diagnosed cases were excluded. Data Collected through Face to face interview was conducted by using closed ended questionnaire (PH-8). Data entered and analysis done by SPSS version 24.

Personal Health Questionnaire Depression Scale (PHQ-8)

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems (Circle one number on each line)

How often have you been bothered by:	Not at all	Several times a day	More than half the days	Nearly Everyday
1. Little interest or pleasure doing things	0	1	2	3
2. Feeling down, depressed or hopeless	0	1	2	3
3. Trouble falling asleep, staying asleep or sleeping too much	0	1	2	3
4. Feeling tired or having little energy	0	1	2	3
5. Poor Appetite or overeating	0	1	2	3
6. Feeling bad about yourself or that you're a failure or have let yourself or your family down	0	1	2	3
7. Trouble concentrating on things such as reading the newspaper or watching television	0	1	2	3
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed or the opposite being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than normal	0	1	2	3
9. Thoughts that you would be better off dead or of hurting yourself in some way	0	1	2	3

Scoring for depression

0-4	No depression
5-9	Mild depression
10-14	Moderate depression
15-19	Moderately severe depression
20-27	Severe depression

RESULTS:

Prevalence of Depression

Age group wise prevalence of depression

Age groups	Depression Criteria				Total
	Mild	Moderate	Moderately Severe	Severe	
31-40	4(33.3%)	6(50%)	0	2(16.7%)	12(100%)
41-50	2(13.3%)	10(66.7%)	3(20%)	0	15(100%)
51-60	0	7(46.7%)	6(40%)	2(13.3%)	15(100%)
61-70	0	0	7(100%)	0	7(100%)
71-80	0	0	4(100%)	0	4(100%)
Total	6(11.6%)	23(43.3%)	20(37.7%)	4(7.5%)	53(100%)

Association of HCV with other diseases

RISK FACTORS OF HCV

Correlation of severity of depression with complications developed

Correlation between Treatment & Depression

Treatment receiving	Depression criteria				total
	Mild	Moderate	Moderately severe	Severe	
Pegelated interferon	0%	6(50%)	6(50%)	0%	12(100%)
Ribavirin	6(19.4%)	15(48.4%)	10(32.3%)	0%	31(100%)
Sofosbuvir	0%	2(100%)	0%	0%	2(100%)
others	0%	0%	4(50%)	4(50%)	8(100%)
Total	6(11.3%)	23(43.4%)	20(37.7%)	4(7.5%)	53(100%)

Taking Antidepressant treatment

DISCUSSION:

The number of people with co-morbid HCV and depressive disorder (including minor depression) increased significantly from 18% to 35% of all people with diagnosed HCV. There are multiple factors responsible for depression in HCV patients; complexity, ambiguity, inconsistency and unpredictability of the course of illness, emotional factors and perception of stigma are thoughts to be the cause of depression in population. Antidepressants are effective in treating interferon alpha/ribavirin associated depression during or after treatment HCV. A multi-disciplinary team should be consulted to develop complex physical and psychological treatments for patients with HCV. Careful monitoring of neuropsychiatric symptoms during antiviral therapy and initiating psychiatric treatment at the initial signs of depression.

CONCLUSION:

We concluded that all the patients with HCV were having some degree of depression. The prevalence of depression was found to be Mild depression 11.3%, Moderate depression 43.3%, moderately severe depression 37.5%, and severe depression 7%. While 37.3% patient develop further complications like hepatic encephalopathy etc.

REFERENCES:

1. Alter HJ, Seeff LB. Recovery, persistence, and sequelae in hepatitis C virus infection: a perspective on long-term outcome. *Semin Liver Dis.* 2000;20:17–35. doi: 10.1055/s-2000-9505. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar].
2. Liver EAfSo. EASL recommendations on treatment of hepatitis C 2015. *J Hepatol.* 2015;63:199. doi: 10.1016/j.jhep.2015.03.025. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
3. Spiegel BM, Younossi ZM, Hays RD, Revicki D, Robbins S, Kanwal F. Impact of hepatitis C

on health related quality of life: a systematic review and quantitative assessment. *Hepatology.* 2005;41:790–800. doi: 10.1002/hep.20659. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]

4. Cho HJ, Park E. Quality of Life of Chronic Hepatitis C Patients and Its Associated Factors. *Osong Public Health Res Perspect.* 2017;8:124–9. doi: 10.24171/j.phrp.2017.8.2.04. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
5. Blasiole JA, Shinkunas L, Labrecque DR, Arnold RM, Zickmund SL. Mental and physical symptoms associated with lower social support for patients with hepatitis C. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2006;12:4665–72. doi: 10.3748/wjg.v12.i29.4665. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
6. Patterson AL, Morasco BJ, Fuller BE, Indest DW, Loftis JM, Hauser P. Screening for depression in patients with hepatitis C using the Beck Depression Inventory-II: do somatic symptoms compromise validity? *Gen Hosp Psychiatry.* 2011;33:354–62. doi: 10.1016/j.genhosppsych.2011.04.005. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
7. McHutchison JG, Ware JE, Jr, Bayliss MS, et al. The effects of interferon alpha-2b in combination with ribavirin on health related quality of life and work productivity. *J Hepatol.* 2001;34:140–7. doi: 10.1016/S0168-8278(00)00026-X. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
8. Younossi Z, Henry L. The impact of the new antiviral regimens on patient reported outcomes and health economics of patients with chronic hepatitis C. *Digest Liver Dis.* 2014;46:S186–S96. doi: 10.1016/j.dld.2014.09.025. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
9. Zigmond AS, Snaith RP. The hospital anxiety and depression scale. *Acta Psychiatr Scand.*

- 1983;67:361–70. doi: 10.1111/j.16000447.1983.tb09716.x. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
10. Aydemir Ö, Guvenir T, Kuey L, Kultur S. Validity and reliability of Turkish version of Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale. *Turk Psikiyatri Derg.* 1997;8:280–7. [Google Scholar]
11. Ware JE, Jr, Sherbourne CD. The MOS 36-item short-form health survey (SF-36). I. Conceptual framework and item selection. *Medical Care.* 1992;30:473–83. doi: 10.1097/00005650-199206000-00002. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
12. Kocyigit H, Aydemir O, Fisek G, Olmez N, Memis A. Validity and reliability of Turkish version of Short form 36: A study of a patients with romatoid disorder. *Turk J Drugs Therap.* 1999;12:102–6. [Google Scholar]
13. Kessler RC, Bromet EJ. The epidemiology of depression across cultures. *Annu Rev Public Health.* 2013;34:119–38. doi: 10.1146/annurev-publhealth-031912-114409. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
14. Pagoto S. Psychological co-morbidities of physical illness: a behavioral medicine perspective. New York: Springer; 2011. [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
15. Ferenci P, Bernstein D, Lalezari J, et al. ABT-450/r-ombitasvir and dasabuvir with or without ribavirin for HCV. *New Eng J Med.* 2014;370:1983–92. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1402338. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
16. Monaco S, Mariotto S, Ferrari S, et al. Hepatitis C virus-associated neurocognitive and neuropsychiatric disorders: Advances in 2015. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2015;21:11974–83. doi: 10.3748/wjg.v21.i42.11974. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
17. Dieperink E, Ho SB, Thuras P, Willenbring ML. A prospective study of neuropsychiatric symptoms associated with interferon-alpha-2b and ribavirin therapy for patients with chronic hepatitis C. *Psychosomatics.* 2003;44:104–12. doi: 10.1176/appi.psy.44.2.104. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
18. Rifai MA, Gleason OC, Sabouni D. Psychiatric care of the patient with hepatitis C: a review of the literature. *Prim Care Companion J Clin Psychiatry.* 2010;12 doi: 10.4088/PCC.09r00877whi. PCC.09r00877. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
19. Carta MG, Hardoy MC, Garofalo A, et al. Association of chronic hepatitis C with major depressive disorders: irrespective of interferon-alpha therapy. *Clin Pract Epidemiol Ment Health.* 2007;3:22. doi: 10.1186/1745-0179-3-22. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
20. Carta MG, Angst J, Moro MF, et al. Association of chronic hepatitis C with recurrent brief depression. *J Affect Disord.* 2012;141:361–6. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2012.03.020. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
21. Yanartas O, Kani HT, Bicakci E, et al. The effects of psychiatric treatment on depression, anxiety, quality of life, and sexual dysfunction in patients with inflammatory bowel disease. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat.* 2019;12:673–83. doi: 10.2147/NDT.S106039. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]